

Phosphorus Oxychloride as a Condensing Agent in the Synthesis of Coumarin Derivatives.

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The subject of the present communication arose from an attempt to condense benzylacetoacetic ester with β -naphthol in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid as the condensing agent. The expected coumarin 3-benzyl-4-methyl-1:2- β -naphthopyrone was not obtained, but methylindene-carboxylic acid was produced by the internal condensation of the ester. α -Naphthol was however, condensed under identical conditions by Ghosh and Jacobson to give the corresponding pyrone derivative (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 424). But on repeating the condensation under the conditions outlined therein, we failed to get the product obtained by them. When concentrated sulphuric acid was replaced by phosphorus oxychloride as the condensing agent, α -naphthol condensed very readily with benzylacetoacetic ester giving the coumarin derivative.

Equimolecular quantities of the phenol and benzylacetoacetic ester were mixed with phosphorus oxychloride (about 0.5 gm. for 2 gms. of the mixture) and the whole heated on the water-bath for about an hour. The mixture was then poured into water, when a solid product separated which was subsequently purified from alcohol.

In each case, excellent yields of crystalline products were obtained. From the physical properties and the melting points of their derivatives, as shown in the adjoining table, the products appeared to be identical with those of Ghosh and Jacobson.

Products obtained from various phenols and benzyl-acetoacetic ester.

Observations by Ghosh & Jacobson.	Phenols.	Resorcinol.	α -Naphthol.	Pyrogallol.	Phloroglucinol.
	Crystalline form	Short, yellow glistening prisma.	Yellow needles	—	Hard, short needles.
	M.p. ...	224°	187°	185°	218°
	M.p. of acetyl derivative ...	168°	—	172°	154°
	M.p. of benzoyl derivative ...	150°	—	184°	—

Observations by the authors.	Phenols.	Resorcinol.	α -Naphthol.	Pyrogallol.	Phloreoglucinol.
Crystalline form		Colourless, glistening prisms.	Pale yellow, slender needles.	Colourless, glistening plates.	Short needles.
M.p.	...	225°	189°-90°	193°	227°
M.p. of acetyl derivative	...	171°	—	172°	158°-59°
M.p. of benzoyl derivative	...	160°	—	181°	124°-25°

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